

BIOcean5D

**MARINE BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND
PREDICTION ACROSS SPATIAL, TEMPORAL
AND HUMAN SCALES**

D1.2 Seatizen kits deployment

Co-funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement number	101059915
Call	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-0
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-03
Type of Action	HORIZON-RIA
Project title	MARINE BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND PREDICTION ACROSS SPATIAL, TEMPORAL AND HUMAN SCALES
Project acronym	BIOcean5D
Deliverable title	Seatizen kits deployment
Deliverable number	D1.2
Version	v1
Document status	Draft
Type	DEM - Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
Diffusion	PU- Public
Related Work Package	WP1: Exploration to fill the marine biodiversity/ecosystem knowledge gap
Task	T1.5
Full lead beneficiary	CNRS - Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
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Due date	M24 - 30.11.2024
Date revised	M31 - 30.06.2025
Submission date	03.07.2025
Total number of pages	42
Keywords	Seatizen science, cost effective tools, plankton, biodiversity.

Table of content

Table of content	2
Version history	4
List of Acronyms	5
Executive summary	6
Introduction	7
Foreword on administrative difficulties	7
1. Instruments deployment strategy	8
1.1. Instruments descriptions	8
1.1.1. Lamprey	8
1.1.2. Planktoscope	9
1.2. Distribution strategy and choice of participants	11
1.2.1. Initial rule framework	11
1.2.2. Diffusion of announcement	12
1.2.3. Choice of participants	12
1.2.3.1. Lamprey workshops	12
1.2.3.2. Planktoscope workshops	13
2. Workshop description	14
2.1. Lamprey workshops	14
2.1.1. Description of content	14
2.1.1.1. General planning	14
2.1.1.2. Standard protocols and communication material	15
2.1.1.3. Sampling and filtration protocols	16
2.1.2. List of Lamprey workshops	16
2.1.3. List of recipients and map of the deployment	16
2.2. Planktoscope workshops	20
2.2.1. Description of content	20
2.2.1.1. General planning	20
2.2.1.2. Material available	20
2.2.2. List of Planktoscope workshops	23
2.2.3. List of recipients and map of the deployment	25
3. Planned use in future / First results	31
3.1. Lamprey	31
3.1.1. General framework	31
3.1.2. Potentiel common use	31
3.1.3. Personal use of participants	31
3.1.4. First results	31
3.2. Planktoscope	31
3.2.1. General framework	31
3.2.2. Potentiel common use	31
3.2.3. Personal use of participants	32
3.2.4. First results	32
3.2.4.1. Results from workshops	32
3.2.4.2. Results from initial participants deployments	32
Conclusion	35
Annexes	36

Annex 1 - Email used to invite potential candidates for the Lamprey and the Planktoscope workshops	36
Annex 2 - Example of detailed program for a Lamprey workshop	38
Annex 3 - Logsheet used to gather standardised metadata related to all Lamprey sampling stations	39
Annex 4 - Example of a taxonomic sheet being produced thanks to the reference project in Ecotaxa - Planktoscope	41

Version history

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
1	C. de Vargas (CNRS), D. Guiffant (SU), E. Legeay (SU), F. Lombard (SU), A. Perruchon (SU), H. Zaccomer (SU)	First version	30.06.2025

List of Acronyms

AI - Artificial Intelligence

APERO - Assessing marine biogenic matter Production, Export and Remineralization : from the surface to the dark Ocean

AWI - Alfred Wegener Institute

COI - cytochrome C oxydase I

DCSMM - Directive-cadre Stratégie pour le milieu marin

DNA - deoxyribonucleic acid

ENA - European Nucleotide Archive

MOOSE - Mediterranean Ocean Observing System for the Environment

MSFD - Marine Strategy Framework Directive

P2 - Plankton Planet

SU - Sorbonne Université

UNOC - United Nations Ocean Conference

WS - Workshop

Executive summary

BIOcean5D has a strong focus on biodiversity exploration, with an emphasis on European coastal marine ecosystems. The project has generated >70K samples from 115 land-to-sea transects from Finland to Greece (T1.1), and >10K samples from 12 sediment cores taken along European coastlines and covering periods from pre-industrial to industrial times (T1.2); it is also analysing decadal trends through comparative plankton time series (T1.3, T1.4). Beyond these exceptional baseline datasets spanning broad spatial and temporal scales, Task 1.5 (T1.5) is focused on developing and deploying simple, collaborative tools and protocols to extend state-of-the-art aquatic biodiversity measurements beyond the lifetime of BIOcean5D. This bottom-up approach aims to scale biodiversity assessments to socio-ecologically and economically relevant levels, while ensuring biodiversity data comparability and integration into a global framework. The primary objective of T1.5 is thus to equip a network of European marine laboratories with cost-effective tools for generating standardized marine biodiversity data, which are directly comparable with those generated in WP1 and contribute to the global plankton data network being developed through the long-run *Plankton Planet* initiative. In this Deliverable (D1.2), we report the successful deployment of PlanktoScopes and Lamprey systems in 61 marine laboratories along the European coastline, from Finland to Crete — and even extending to Cyprus and Eilat in Israel. These cost-effective instruments enable the assessment of aquatic biodiversity through, respectively, quantitative imaging and DNA metabarcoding. To ensure maximum efficiency and long-term impact, the deployment followed several successive phases: (i) Finalization of the instruments and associated protocols; (ii) A pan-European call for expressions of interest, which received positive responses from over 100 marine laboratories; (iii) Organization of 12 training workshops at the marine stations of Villefranche-sur-Mer (PlanktoScope) and Roscoff (Lamprey), involving 115 participants from 61 marine labs from 20 countries; (iv) Co-design of a collective time-series plankton sampling program to be implemented in 2025–2026. A distinctive feature of these workshops is their comprehensive, hands-on approach. Participants are trained in the entire workflow — from plankton sampling and field deployment of the instruments, to data and metadata generation, management, and analysis. This full-process training, spanning from fieldwork to knowledge production, was highly valued by participants. Many have now begun sampling their local ecosystems and have committed to making their data FAIR and publicly available via standardized data papers, enabling transnational and multiscale comparative analyses. Overall, this has been an enriching collective learning experience: the T1.5 team was able to directly test and refine the tools in collaboration with European colleagues, while the trainees gained access to simple and cost-effective protocols that open new possibilities for exploring biodiversity at unprecedented spatial and temporal scales. We also explored all together opportunities to further extend the reach of these tools and bottom-up strategy through future collaborations with marine professionals — including for instance fish farmers, fishers, sailors, and cargo crews.

Introduction

BIOcean5D has a strong focus on biodiversity exploration, with an emphasis on European coastal marine ecosystems. As part of the TREC expedition, the project has generated over 70,000 samples across 115 land-to-sea transects, from Finland to Greece, to establish a pan-European baseline of marine biodiversity in water, sediments, and aerosols (T1.1). To address biodiversity changes over time, BIOcean5D has collected more than 10,000 samples from 12 sediment cores taken along European coastlines, covering periods from pre-industrial to industrial times (T1.2). In parallel, it is analysing decadal trends through comparative plankton time series (T1.3, T1.4). Beyond these exceptional baseline datasets spanning broad spatial and temporal scales, Task 1.5 (T1.5) is focused on developing and deploying simple, collaborative tools and protocols to extend state-of-the-art aquatic biodiversity measurements beyond the lifetime of BIOcean5D. This bottom-up approach aims to scale biodiversity assessments to socio-ecologically and economically relevant levels, while ensuring data comparability and integration into a global framework. The primary objective of T1.5 is thus to equip a network of approximately 50 European marine laboratories with cost-effective tools for generating standardized marine biodiversity data, which are directly comparable with those generated in Work Package 1 (WP1) and contribute to the global plankton data network being developed through the long-run Plankton Planet initiative. Deliverable 1.2 (D1.2) presents the finalization of these cost-effective instruments and protocols, their transfer to 61 partner laboratories through 12 training workshops held at the Villefranche-sur-Mer and Roscoff marine stations, and the future data outputs anticipated from this network. By adopting a shared, frugal, and bottom-up strategy for marine biodiversity monitoring, this community of laboratories is positioned to generate high-quality, comparable datasets for long-term, large/multi-scales, and collaborative assessments of marine aquatic biodiversity.

Foreword on administrative difficulties

Some administrative difficulties were responsible for a >9 months delay in the ordering of the Planktosopes. After ordering the 10 first units, our university (SU) realised that a public contract for supplies needed to be opened before proceeding with the rest of the purchases, which took months to complete. Additionally, the engineer responsible for logistics and training returned to study after one year and was replaced, which generated additional delay.

Foreword on change on strategic choice of deployment

During Proposal and Grant Agreement preparations, the Task foresaw the distribution of 50 kits to professional users of the sea. At that time, testing of these cost-effective, innovative instruments and associated protocols developed by the Plankton Planet team was not fully completed. In the first year of the project, it became apparent that scientific support would be necessary to use the instruments. Hence, the deployment strategy was revised, in order to create a solid network of scientific institutes as the basis for future transfer of protocols and knowledge to local “sea-tizens”. During all workshops held as part of T1.5, the trained scientists were encouraged to connect and participate in such local deployments.

1. Instruments deployment strategy

1.1. Instruments descriptions

1.1.1. Lamprey

The Lamprey is a miniaturized and versatile wet-lab bench enclosed in a pelicase. It allows easy and systematic concentration of plankton biomass from various plankton size-fractions onto filter-membranes, using either battery-powered peristaltic pumping or manual pumping using a large syringe. Filter-membranes are then either preserved into a buffer and stored in the fridge, or simply dried and stored at room temperature, depending on field conditions, before their processing in the lab.

Figure 1.1 - Lamprey system on the field for net sampling during 3rd workshop at the Roscoff Marine Station., Credits: PAQUE Cyann

Figure 1.2 - Lamprey filtration system in its battery-powered peristaltic pump version. A) Filter holder, B) Tweezers, C) Wash bottle, D) Silicone tubing, E) Membrane, F) Tube holder, G) Potentiometer, H) Lithium battery / Waterproof box, I) Peristaltic pump, J) Bleach tube.

Very importantly, standard protocols for plankton sampling, DNA extractions and metabarcoding are taught to all collaborators, allowing the local measures to be compared globally.

Developed in the framework of the Plankton Planet (P2) initiative (<https://planktonplanet.org/>), the Lamprey is distributed today by the SeaLabX company.

1.1.2. Planktoscope

The PlanktoScope (Fig. 2) is a cost-effective, microfluidic flow-through microscope designed with an open-hardware and open-software approach. It was conceived with the idea of providing scientists and sailors exploring the oceans with a field instrument suitable for quantitative imaging of aquatic micro-biodiversity. With its capacity to operate high-precision imaging of suspended particles, it can capture details of plankton morphology up to 300 μm , enabling quantitative planktonic studies. It offers a balance between budget constraints and the need for semi-automated quantitative microscopy.

Originally developed in the framework of the Plankton Planet initiative (<https://planktonplanet.org/>), the Planktoscope is now a distributed instrument by the company Fairscope (<https://www.fairscope.com/>). The version deployed in the BIOcean5D project is version 2.6.

Figure 2: Schematic view of the PlanktoScope 2.6 (image by Pierre Kostyrka)

The PlanktoScope automatically captures images of plankton (20-300 μm); it then captures various morphological measurements to produce an image archive which can be directly imported within EcoTaxa (<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/>), where taxonomic annotation is possible with AI assisted procedures.

Figure 3: examples of plankton images obtained with the Planktoscope (here copepod nauplii, acantharians; coccolithophores, tintinids, dinoflagellates, diatoms radiolarians and ctenophore juveniles). Crédits Karine Leblanc .

Figure 4: Examples of plankton images obtained with the Planktoscope and downloaded into EcoTaxa, a web-platform allowing automatic classification using AI followed by expert fine tuning.

1.2. Distribution strategy and choice of participants

In order to maximise the efficiency and long-term impact of the deployment of cost-effective tools to assess plankton biodiversity in the frame of BIOcean5D, we decided to primarily target scientists from European marine stations, with expertise in microplankton and/or DNA metabarcoding, and will to work in the future with non-scientist sea users and sea farers.

1.2.1. Initial rule framework

All participants in the workshops had to agree on a set of rules, shown in the box below.

Community agreement BOX

About 50 Planktoscopes and Lampreys will be distributed, for free, across European laboratories in the frame of the BIOcean5D EU co-funded project. The project covers the costs of the instruments, some consumables, some sequencing (for ca. 80 Lamprey samples per participating lab), and training on the instruments protocols and data management/analyses; in exchange the participating teams/labs should agree upon a set of basic rules underlying the collective and frugal approach promoted in (P2) to change scale toward the measurement of standardized plankton data for planetary systems biology:

1. **Data quality and uniformity.** At least one person from the participating labs has to follow a BIOcean5D P2 workshop detailing how to use the Planktoscope, the Lamprey, or both. Ideally two lab members would join and be trained, the person who will be using the instrument and someone who will analyse the data. The condition for receiving the instrument is a mandatory participation in this workshop and lab training.
2. **Inter-sites calibration and comparison.** Participating labs will be part of a joint time-series like sampling effort. A common sampling period and frequency will be defined with all the participants to optimize an intercomparison experiment. About half of the BIOcean5D consumables and sequencing capacity provided will be dedicated to this collective effort. Participating labs will have total freedom for deployment of the instruments and protocols beyond this collective effort, based on the other half of the BIOcean5D consumables/sequencing capacity, and further supplies at the discretion of the participating labs (in the case of the Planktoscope, no consumables nor analysing capacities are provided). Participating labs will be encouraged to develop strategies to deploy and use the instruments in collaboration with citizen initiatives, as well as share their sampling plans with the other participating labs.
3. **Data FAIRness and property.** Data generated in the frame of the joint sampling effort will be openly shared between participants. Data will be public for their valorisation in a scientific article (data paper) listing all the participants as authors. Data generated beyond this joint sampling effort are the property and responsibility of each participating lab. The BIOcean5D team will request basic samples/data information (number of samples, number of images/sequences acquired, spatio-temporal context) to report statistical monitoring to the European Commission. Ultimately, and at least after their publication, all data must follow the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles requested by the European Commission, as described in BIOcean 5D - D3.1 Data Management Plan.
4. **Instruments property and usage.** The instruments become the property of the participating labs. However, if an instrument is not used, the participating lab should return it to the trainers from CNRS and SU for deployment with other partners.

1.2.2. Diffusion of announcement

D1.2 - Seatizen kits deployment

This initiative was announced, together with an online form (see Annex 1), via emails to scientists known in the community and fitting the above description, as well as to the network of EMBRC (European Marine Biological Resource Center) marine stations, to all BIOcean5D's members and marine laboratories associated to the TREC expedition (see D1.1). Representatives from 29 recent or ongoing European projects were finally contacted and invited to circulate the announcement within their own networks.

Our online form (<https://form.jotform.com/241332163991051>) collected responses from 102 different laboratories across Europe and beyond.

1.2.3. Choice of participants

As part of the outreach campaign, interested individuals were invited to complete an online questionnaire designed to better understand their specific needs and to assess the relevance of their proposed projects within the scope of BIOcean5D Task 1.5.

Several criteria were evaluated, including but not limited to:

- Interest in the Lamprey and/or Planktoscope instruments
- Involvement in European research networks related to plankton ecology and evolution
- Interest in citizen science approaches
- Expertise in fields such as ecology, taxonomy, microscopy, quantitative imaging, environmental genomics, and metabarcoding

The survey also asked applicants to indicate their willingness to comply with community-based rules including:

- Access to equipment being conditional on participation in dedicated workshops
- Involvement in a collaborative time-series exercise following a standardized protocol
- Adherence to FAIR data-sharing principles
- Commitment to actively use and maintain the provided devices

A total of 100 individuals responded to the survey:

- 70 respondents expressed interest in both the Lamprey and the Planktoscope
- 23 respondents were interested exclusively in the Planktoscope
- 7 respondents expressed interest only in the Lamprey

1.2.3.1. Lamprey workshops

Several criteria were considered in selecting participants for the Lamprey training workshops and for the allocation of filtration systems.

The workshops were aimed at European marine laboratories interested in plankton ecology. Ideally, one person with a molecular ecology background and a second person familiar with the analysis of sequencing data would join from every invited partner lab.

We also targeted an equilibrated sampling span, trying to distribute instruments homogeneously along the European coastlines.

D1.2 - Seatizen kits deployment

The organization of these workshops was subject to logistical constraints specific to the Roscoff site. The availability of teaching facilities, as well as capacity limits for accommodation and catering, significantly restricted the scheduling options during the 2024–2025 period. As a result, group composition was also influenced by participant availability on the fixed workshop dates.

For each session, a waiting list was established to ensure the optimal distribution of available Lamprey units, in line with the number of instruments that could be produced for each time slot.

As of time of publication (June 2025), a list of individuals who were interested but not able to participate has been maintained. These individuals will be given priority consideration, should an additional workshop be organized before the end of 2025.

1.2.3.2. Planktoscope workshops

Several criteria were considered in selecting the participants in the Planktoscope workshop and for the allocation of instruments. First, using the list of known marine laboratories, we considered participants residing close to the coast. As the Planktoscope requires some combined knowledge of microscopic instruments, taxonomy, data analyses and potential for sampling opportunities, we then favored scientists with:

- some taxonomic knowledge on microplankton (phyto or zoo components)
- prior knowledge on using quantitative imaging tools or microscopic tools
- have the possibility to regularly sample their local ecosystems.

Furthermore, an homogeneous sampling of the European coast was also targeted and we tried to distribute instruments homogeneously across coastlines. The initial plan of deployment was determined as described on the map in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Original “ideal” plan of deployment of the P2 tool-kit (each points corresponding to a marine laboratory)

2. Workshop description

2.1. Lamprey workshops

2.1.1. Description of content

2.1.1.1. General planning

All workshops were held in the Station Biologique de Roscoff and supported by the following members and trainers:

- Damien Guiffant, general organisation,
- Erwan Legeay, technical part of the Lamprey use (theory and practical),
- Morgan Guillam, technical part of the Lamprey use (practical),
- Nicolas Henry, bioinformatics and biostatistics - analyses of metabarcoding data,
- Colombar de Vargas, link to Plankton Planet, leading discussions amongst participants regarding future sampling in the frame of BIOcean5D and beyond.
- Noan Le Bescot, from SeaLabX, technical support and presentation of other P2 cost-effective tools, such as the Planktoscope and the Curiosity microscope.

All workshops were held over three days and organised followed a similar structure:

- **Introductory Session:** The first half-day began with a presentation of the trainers, followed by an overview of the BIOcean5D project, its Task 1.5, and the objectives of the workshops. Each participant was then invited to introduce themselves, present the work of their research group, and explain how the *Lamprey* approach could be relevant to their activities.
- **Thematic Days:** The following two full days were dedicated to the presentation and practical use of the *Lamprey* system and associated protocols, from plankton biomass sampling to sample processing for sequencing, and subsequent DNA metabarcoding analyses. A half-day session was organized during which participants collected plankton samples using a plankton net, operated the *Lamprey* and trained on the filtration protocol. This session was also an opportunity to present other cost-effective tools developed by Plankton Planet, such as the *Planktoscope* and the *Curiosity microscope*. One full day was then dedicated to learn simple bioinformatic analytical workflows for metabarcoding data analyses using R, with an initial theoretical introduction to the concepts as well as hands-on sessions. The scheduling of these sessions varied slightly from one workshop to another, depending on weather conditions and tidal times, which determined the most suitable time slots for fieldwork.
- **Closing Session:** At each workshop's final half-day, the organisers and participants discussed and co-designed the coordinated, BIOcean5D collective plankton time series sampling effort, to be realized by all involved partners along the year to come. At the end of the last workshop, all participants, including those from the first two workshops, were invited to a one-hour visio-conference to finalize the collective sampling roadmap (see below).

As an illustration, an example of a detailed program is provided in Annex 2.

2.1.1.2. Standard protocols and communication material

Several materials were developed and provided to participants during and after (updates) the workshop:

- A website was built to share the presentations' slides and the protocols - including analytical workflows and instructions - with the participants : <https://lamprey-workshops.gitlab.io/data-analyses-course-material/>
- A '*Collective Sampling Roadmap*' was shared following the last workshop. Its content is based on the discussions held with all participants during each closing session and lays the groundwork for a year-long collaborative monitoring effort along the European coasts. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15739397>
- A detailed '*Lamprey plankton sampling*' protocol was developed and shared to ensure that sample collection, filtration and preservation are carried out in a standardized manner by all participating laboratories. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15739225>

D1.2 - Seatizen kits deployment

- A logsheet was created in order to gather standardised metadata related to all sampling stations. This document is provided in Annex 3. All data collected through this tool will be gathered in a table publicly published at ENA.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15739303>
- Logsheet instructions were shared in order to correctly fill in the logsheet.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15739243>
- Four Slack channels were created to facilitate communication between participants and the Roscoff team. All workshop participants are encouraged to discuss the sampling protocol, to report any technical issues related to the plankton net or the Lamprey system itself, and to suggest possible improvements to the system and the protocol.

2.1.1.3. Sampling and filtration protocols

A detailed protocol was developed, covering all steps from plankton sampling to filtration and sample labeling :

- Checklist before sampling
- Plankton net tow sampling
- Plankton concentration onto filter membranes
- Final cleaning
- Samples labelling and metadata

There are two versions of this protocol :

- v1.0, November 2024: shared during the three workshops
- v2.0, April 2025: finalized after the first three workshops, and distributed as the final protocol to follow for the collective plankton times-series across European coastlines.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15739225>

2.1.2. List of Lamprey workshops

Workshop Nb	Dates	Lamprey #	Nb of participants	Nb of labs
WS1	12-15 Nov 2024	1-4	7	4
WS2	20-23 Jan 2025	5-14	13	10
WS3	15-18 April 2025	15-25	16	11

2.1.3. List of recipients and map of the deployment

Workshop number	Recipient number#	Institute	Location	Country	Nb of participants
1	1	VLIZ	Ostend	Belgium	1
	2	Oceanography Department, Institute of Marine Research IIM-CSIC	Vigo	Spain	2
	3	Departamento de Ecoloxía e Bioloxía animal, Centro de	Vigo	Spain	2

Workshop number	Recipient number#	Institute	Location	Country	Nb of participants
		Investigación Mariña, Universidade de Vigo			
	4	Université de Caen-Normandie, CREC-Station marine	Luc sur Mer	France	2
2	5	NORCE	Bergen	Norway	2
	6	MARBEC CNRS	Montpellier	France	2
	7	Université de Montpellier, OSU OREME	Sète	France	1
	8	National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics (OGS)	Trieste	Italy	2
	9	Finnish Environment Institute Syke	Oulu	Finland	1
	10	IMR	Bergen	Norway	1
	11	AZTI	Pasaia	Spain	1
	12	Dokuz Eylul University Institute of Marine Science and Technology	Izmir	Turkey	1
	13	CCMAR/EMBRC-PT	Faro	Portugal	1
	14	NTNU, Phytoplankton lab	Trondheim	Norway	1
3	15	Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn	Napoli	Italy	2
	16	IFREMER	La Tremblade	France	2
	17	DTU Aqua	Kongens Lyngby	Denmark	1
	18	Tvärminne Zoological Station/University of Helsinki	Helsinki	Finland	2
	19	National Marine Fisheries Research Institute	Gdynia	Poland	1
	20	Ruppin Academic Center, Marine Microbes Lab	Michmoret	Israel	2
	21	EMBL	Heidelberg	Germany	2
	22	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences	Brussels	Belgium	1
	23	BOREA MNHN- Le Mans Université	Concarneau	France	1
	24	Instituto Español de Oceanografía (CSIC) - Laboratorio Biogeoquímica	Santa Cruz de Tenerife	Spain	1
	25	Dove Marine Laboratory – Newcastle University	Newcastle	England	1

Figure 6: Sites where a Lamprey kit was distributed, in the framework of BIOcean5D, as of June 2025. Lamprey were distributed over 3 different workshops (WS1 in green, WS2 in blue and WS3 in purple).

Pictures from Lamprey workshop #1: left: group picture, right: participants being trained on the use of the instrument

Pictures from Lamprey workshop #2: left: Lamprey instruments in their cases, ready to be distributed, right: group picture

Pictures from Lamprey workshop #3: left: group picture, right: sampling at the Roscoff ee marina with plankton nets.

2.2. Planktoscope workshops

2.2.1. Description of content

For practical and logistic reasons (easy access to classrooms with both internet, sinks and powerplugs, to fresh plankton sampling twice a day) most workshops were located in Villefranche-sur-Mer (two exceptions see 2.2.2) and limited to 10 Planktoscopes for 20 participants.

2.2.1.1. General planning

The same program (table below) was applied for every training workshop (see below). This program gives a strong practical experience on the instrument by using it more than 70% of the time and running at least 3 samples. This also allowed triplicate use of every machine on the same sample, further allowing intercalibration or detection of misuses in the protocol, together with quantification of the potential impact of those biases.

	Morning	Afternoon
Monday		General presentation (B5D, planktoscope), first use of planktoscope, mounting, assembling, connecting
Tuesday	Calibration of the planktoscope, demonstration on how to pass a sample	Practical first use on a sample: from metadata to processing sample
Wednesday	using ecotaxa (importing, predicting, annotating)	Practical second use on a sample: up to ecotaxa annotations
Thursday	Practical third use on a sample: up to ecotaxa annotations (eventually 4th sample)	Analysing results Simple analysis (ecotaxa export/ excell) Complex analysis (R, Matlab etc)
Friday	Packing, General discussion on future sampling Networking future	

2.2.1.2. Material available

In order to provide an efficient training, several tools were developed and provided to participants during and after (updates) the workshops. This covers a detailed protocol (which served as a backbone for training), analytical pipelines under R and MatLab codes, as well as taxonomic reference resources.

Protocols

A full practical protocol was produced and openly available in the links below. It covers the following topics (table of content), which correspond to the different parts of the training workshop:

- Introduction
- Quick usage version
- Quality Checks reminder
- Assemble the PlanktoScope
- User Interface and initial connection
- Size calibration
- White Balance calibration
- Pump calibration
- Get your sample
- Pass the sample on PlanktoScope
- Segment the acquisition
- How to export data
- Clean the PlanktoScope
- Upload your images on EcoTaxa
- How to use efficiently EcoTaxa
- How to compute biovolumes
- Maintenance of your PlanktoScope
- Troubleshooting
- External links

Three incremental versions of the protocol were produced:

1. Protocol v3

Pierre Kostyrka, Lombard Fabien 2024. Planktoscope protocol for plankton imaging. [protocols.io](https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bp2l6bq3zgqe/v3)
<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bp2l6bq3zgqe/v3>

2. Protocol v4

Adélaïde Perruchon, Hugo Zaccomer, Lombard Fabien 2025. PlanktoScope protocol for plankton imaging. [protocols.io](https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bp2l6bq3zgqe/v4)
<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bp2l6bq3zgqe/v4>

3. Protocol v5 (in prep.)

Adélaïde Perruchon, Hugo Zaccomer, Lombard Fabien 2025. PlanktoScope protocol for plankton imaging. [protocols.io](https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bp2l6bq3zgqe/v5)
<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bp2l6bq3zgqe/v5>

Analysis pipeline

A common framework to analyse data from the Planktoscope allows samples' cross-comparison. We thus created an analytical pipeline in R and Matlab, allowing efficient assessment of metadata quality, as well as computation of plankton taxa abundances or biovolumes, for further multivariate analyses. This ensures a common analytical framework for data quality check, and provides standard tools to unveil potential signals in the dataset (Fig. 7). This pipeline is still in development for multivariate analysis. We plan to integrate it as a Github package and to publish it as a methodological paper in 2025. These pipelines are currently accessible on github (<https://github.com/zoemgt/ecotaxatools> for Matlab; <https://github.com/Adeelaiide/ECotaxaTools> for R).

Figure 7. Description of a sampling station from the workshop using the R pipeline. This graphics allow quick visualisation of (i) the total abundance, biovolume and diversity (Shannon) of organisms in the sample; (ii) the different taxonomic and trophic groups composing the analyzed population; (iii) the biovolume size spectra (BSS), normalized biovolume size spectra (NBSS), and relative biovolumes by size classes - a complete display of the size spectra composition of the community.

Taxonomic reference project

In order to facilitate the taxonomic sorting of plankton images captured by the Planktoscope, we have also built a common taxonomic reference project on EcoTaxa, using Planktoscope data acquired across several missions and settings, notably in the framework of Plankton Planet and the mission Bougainville project, during the APERO and MOOSE GE oceanographic cruises, and during the BIOcean5D workshops. This approach presents the advantage to capture a wide and diverse set of examples from several oceans.

Figure 8: Map of geographical origin of Planktoscope samples and data used to construct the Planktoscope reference dataset.

Figure 9: example of image from one diatom genus - *Climacodium sp.*

This taxonomic reference project is growing; as of June 2025, it includes >129 000 images of plankton sorted within 303 morphological taxonomic units, and available at: <https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/15535>. In addition to this reference dataset and in preparation for a BIOcean5D taxonomic summer school in 2025-2026 (T7.3), several descriptive taxonomic plates are also under construction to propose a FAIR and collaborative approach of taxonomy in planktoscopy. These plates can be found here : <https://ecotaxoguide.imev-mer.fr/search/general>, and one example is provided in Annex 4.

2.2.2. List of Planktoscope workshops

Planktoscope training workshops happened into two phases. The first phase targeted French laboratories to also test and refine the teaching procedure and material, while the second phase targeted other, non-french european countries.

D1.2 - Seatizen kits deployment

Planktoscope workshop #	Date	Number of participants	Country, Location	Trainers	Ecotaxa link (direct access to the images and datasets collected)
1	04-08.12.2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 16 individuals • 6 institutes • 5 kits 	France, Villefranche sur Mer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabien Lombard • Pierre Kostyrka • Amanda Elineau 	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/11093
2	15-19.01.2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 individuals • 5 institutes • 3 kits 	France, Villefranche sur Mer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabien Lombard • Pierre Kostyrka • Zoe Mériguet 	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/11461
3	02-04.04.2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 individuals • 2 institutes • 2 kits 	France, La Rochelle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pierre Kostyrka 	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/12250
4	02-06.12.2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 13 individuals • 9 institutes • 8 kits 	France, Villefranche sur Mer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabien Lombard • Adélaïde Perruchon 	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/14945
5	13- 17.01.2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 17 individuals • 11 institutes • 9 kits 	France, Villefranche sur Mer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabien Lombard • Adélaïde Perruchon 	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/15217
6	3-7.03.2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 11 individuals • 8 institutes • 8 kits 	France, Villefranche sur Mer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabien Lombard • Adélaïde Perruchon • Hugo Zaccomer 	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/16115
7	24-29.03.2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 11 individuals • 8 institutes • 7 kits 	France, Villefranche sur Mer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabien Lombard • Adélaïde Perruchon • Hugo Zaccomer 	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/16392
8	05-09.05.2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10 individuals • 1 institute • 1 kit 	Portugal, Azores, Horta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adélaïde Perruchon 	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/16856
9	19-23.05.2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 individuals • 7 institutes • 7 kits 	France, Villefranche sur Mer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fabien Lombard • Adélaïde Perruchon • Hugo Zaccomer 	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/17018

One workshop took place exceptionally in the Azores, to train an entire local team, and one workshop took place in La Rochelle for the few French participants that couldn't join either of the first two workshops.

Pictures taken during the last workshop

Figure 10: Left side: participants in one of the practicals session ; Right side: group picture

2.2.3. List of recipients and map of the deployment

In total 50 Planktoscope kits were deployed into 19 countries and 97 people were trained to use the instrument during the 9 training workshops organized (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Final Map of the deployment of the 50 Planktoscope kits for cost-effective plankton quantitative imaging.

Some laboratories were already equipped with a Planktoscope prior to the BIOcean5D workshop series (self funded acquisition or prior presence in one workshop but additional

D1.2 - Seatizen kits deployment

BIOcean5D

demand of training), and asked for training, and therefore did not receive an additional unit; These institutes are labelled with ** in the table below.

Planktoscope workshop number	Recipient number	Institute	Location	Country	number of participants
1	1	Laboratoire d'Océanologie et de Géosciences	Wimereux	France	3
	2	Institut de la mer de Villefranche	Villefranche sur Mer	France	5
	3	MARBEC (Marine Biodiversity Exploitation and Conservation)	Montpellier	France	4
	4	Mediterranean Institute of Oceanology (MIO)	Marseille	France	1
	5	Station Biologique de Roscoff	Roscoff	France	1
	**	ETH Zurich	Zurich	Switzerland	2
2	6	Station Marine Banyuls	Banyuls	France	2
	7	IUEM Brest	Brest	France	1
	8	EPOC, Bordeaux	Arcachon	France	1
	**	Mediterranean Institute of Oceanology (MIO)	Marseille	France	1
	**	Station Biologique de Roscoff	Roscoff	France	3
3	9	LIENS	La Rochelle	France	1
	10	IFREMER	Lorient	France	2
4	11	AWI	Bremerhaven	Germany	2
	12	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ) - Marine Observation Centre division	Ostend	Belgium	2
	13	MARE-Madeira	Funchal	Portugal	2
	14	Plymouth Marine Laboratory	Plymouth	UK	1
	15	AMBER lab	Haifa	Israël	1
	16	NTNU	Trondheim	Norway	2

D1.2 - Seatizen kits deployment

Planktoscope workshop number	Recipient number	Institute	Location	Country	number of participants
	17	Cefas	Lowestoft	UK	1
	18	PIE-UPV/EHU. University of the Basque Country	Getxo	Spain	1
	**	Station Biologique de Roscoff	Roscoff	France	1
5	19	Centro de Investigación Marina, University of Vigo	Vigo	Spain	2
	20	MARE	Peniche	Portugal	1
	21	Marine microbiology- University of Bergen	Bergen	Norway	2
	22	DTU Aqua	Copenhagen	Denmark	1
	23	Laboratory of Plankton Biology, Department of Marine Biology and Biotechnology, University of Gdansk	Gdynia	Poland	2
	24	NORCE	Bergen	Norway	1
	25	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale-OGS	Trieste	Italy	2
	26	Department of Oceanography, CSIC - Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas	Vigo	Spain	2
	27	Senckenberg, DZMB	Hamburg	Germany	2
	**	Plymouth Marine Laboratory	Plymouth	UK	1
	**	FairScope	Morlaix	France	1
6	28	HCMR	Athens	Greece	2
	29	Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn	Napoli	Italy	2
	30	Faculty of Biosciences and aquaculture, Nord University	Bodø	Norway	2
	31	NOC	Southampton	UK	1

D1.2 - Seatizen kits deployment

Planktoscope workshop number	Recipient number	Institute	Location	Country	number of participants
	32	Marine Research Station, University of Gothenburg	Kristineberg and Tjärnö	Sweden	1
	33	Finnish Environment Institute Syke	Helsinki	Finland	1
	34	The Hebrew University of Jerusalem	Eilat	Israël	1
	35	Spanish Institute of Oceanography	Teneriff	Spain	1
7	36	Plankton Ecology and Environmental Challenges. Spanish Institute of Oceanography - CSIC	Malaga	Spain	2
	37	Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM-CSIC)	Barcelona	Spain	2
	38	Tvärminne Zoological Station, University of Helsinki	Hanko	Finland	1
	39	University of Milan-Bicocca and Marine Research and High Education (MaRHE) Center	Milan	Italy	1
	40	Institute of Oceanography, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research	Heraklion	Greece	2
	41	Institute for marine and coastal research, University of Dubrovnik	Dubrovnik	Croatia	1
	42	Dove Marine Laboratory – Newcastle University	Newcastle	UK	1
	**	ETH Zurich	Zurich	Switzerland	1
8	43	IICM-OKEANOS	Horta	Portugal	10
9	44	Lund University	Lund	Sweden	1
	45	Norwegian Institute for Water Research	Oslo	Norway	1
	46	NIMRD, Department of Ecology and Marine Biology	Constanta	Romania	1
	47	Lyell Centre, Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh	Edinburgh	Scotland	2
	48	The Laboratory for Evolutionary Ecology at the Center	Rovinj	Croatia	1

Co funded by the European Union (GA# 101059915). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

D1.2 - Seatizen kits deployment

Planktoscope workshop number	Recipient number	Institute	Location	Country	number of participants
		for Marine Research			
	49	CCMAR	Faro	Portugal	1
	50	CMMI	Larnaca	Cyprus	1

Co funded by the European Union (GA# 101059915). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

3. Planned use in future / First results

3.1. Lamprey

3.1.1. General framework

Participants are equipped with all the tools and protocols necessary to ensure the collection and generation of plankton samples for genetic analysis. The first 80 samples will be handled in the frame of BIOcean5D for further analysis (DNA extraction, PCR amplification of keystone marker genes, sequencing, bioinformatics data quality check and taxonomic annotation) with only the cost of the shipping to Roscoff for them.

3.1.2. Potentiel common use

At the end of the third workshop, a common sampling exercise (*Lamprey* collective plankton time series) was planned with the 25 participating sites. This will take the form of a bi-monthly coastal time series over a period of one year, starting in the Summer 2025.

3.1.3. Personal use of participants

Participants have an additional >50 free samples (sequenced at Genoscope as part of T1.6), to explore any plankton ecological patterns of interest in their location. In the future, they will hopefully adopt the Lamprey system in their routine field work, they can buy other units and use Lamprey system(s) to explore exceptional ecological spatio-temporal scales, in particular with economical actors of the sea (fish or shellfish farmers, fishermen, crews, MPA managers, etc), while generating standard plankton data than can be compared globally.

3.1.4. First results

We expect that each partner team/lab will generate 80 samples by the end of 2026, based on collective and individual sampling plans, for a total and their own activities for a total of 2000 samples, sequenced with 3 different markers (16S-V4V5, 18S-V9 and COI).

3.2. Planktoscope

3.2.1. General framework

Users are requested to identify their projects into EcoTaxa (by putting "BIOCEAN5D" in the title), to facilitate *a posteriori* retrieval of the published projects, for potential global comparisons and visibility.

3.2.2. Potentiel common use

As for the Lamprey system, we plan to initiate a regular synchronous sampling by the participating teams, for a large-scale, homogenous, and cost-effective monitoring of European marine coastal waters. If successful, this may generate a common indicator of ecosystem health (Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) // Directive Cadre « Stratégie pour le Milieu Marin » (DCSMM)) at the scale of Europe. Now that all instruments are deployed, the BIOcean5D Planktoscope time series may start soon. However, participants are also warned that the BIOcean5D project has no additional resources to support quantitative imaging data analyses (not planned/ funded as part of the Grant Agreement) which then rely on local efforts or funding from other sources.

3.2.3. Personal use of participants

Participants are strongly encouraged to use the instrument for their personal research work, cruises, citizen science initiatives, they can also buy additional units to cover denser and/or wider ecological scales, but are also warned that the BIOcean5D project is not providing analytical support.

3.2.4. First results

The initial observations helped the identification of different methodological biases that may impact the final results of potential bugs in the Planktoscope Software (reported and corrected). Additionally, the recipients have already started deployment locally.

3.2.4.1. Results from workshops

The workshops highlighted critical biases in the use of the Planktoscope, impacting the number of organisms imaged, which translate into biases in the results from the data analysis. For example, if the bubbler is not switched on, the sample will lack homogeneity, with plankton sedimenting at the bottom. Thus, the imaged part will show higher abundances than the reality, leading to overestimation of quantities. Identifying these biases enabled us to greatly improve the protocol. Additionally, recurring errors made by the participants during the workshops helped identify some challenging aspects in the use of the tool, but also to quantify the impact of different biases resulting from improper protocol use. We improved the protocols to highlight these challenging areas. Feedback from the participants also led to improvements in the software, making it more user-friendly, as well as to suggestions for improvements in the hardware to be implemented in the next version of Planktoscope (first prototypes will soon be available). Moreover, samples from the workshops have contributed to the construction of the taxonomic reference project in Ecotaxa, which will serve as a learning dataset for multiple users (see chapter 2.2.1.2). Finally and importantly, the workshops made the intercalibration of instruments possible, which will enable comparison of the data from the European monitoring network to be set up in the near future.

3.2.4.2. Results from initial participants deployments

As of June 2025, participants have started to deploy and use the Planktoscope they received (see Figure 12 below).

Figure 12: Localisation and date of collection (colours) of the samples collected using the BIOcean5D Planktoscope network.

The full list of projects originating from BIOcean5D Planktoscope units is given below (one link corresponding to one project originating from one Planktoscope used in a given context - e.g. a cruise, time series, experiment-, one Planktoscope being potentially used for several projects):

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/11280>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/11281>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/11677>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/11937>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/12444>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/12445>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/12588>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/13290>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/13553>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/13554>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/13943>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/14080>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/15032>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/15107>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/15187>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/15219>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/15227>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/15374>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16244>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16245>

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<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16250>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16280>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16285>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16401>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16549>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16589>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16604>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16609>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16842>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16884>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16933>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/17013>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/15762>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/15763>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/15781>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16030>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16059>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16135>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16140>

<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/17173>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/17239>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/17290>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/17298>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/17317>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16242>
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/gui/prj/16243>

Additionally, the planktoscope was used for different actions by the participating teams/labs, including deployments:

- during plankton courses: <https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/17239>
- during a UNOC plankton side event (on 09/06/2025 - see Fig 13):
<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/17298>
- aboard a sailing boat going to UNOC from Tromsø to Nice (120 samples not yet available on EcoTaxa)
- at the Baltic Sea Science Congress

Figure 13: Planktoscope demonstration at UNOC - 09.06.2025 by recipients from AWI

Conclusion

We have successfully deployed PlanktoScopes and Lamprey systems in 61 marine laboratories from 20 countries along the European coastline, from Finland to Crete — and even extending to Cyprus and Eilat in Israel. These cost-effective instruments enable the assessment of aquatic biodiversity through, respectively, quantitative imaging and DNA metabarcoding. To ensure maximum efficiency and long-term impact, the deployment followed several successive phases: (i) Finalization of the instruments and associated protocols; (ii) A pan-European call for expressions of interest, which received positive responses from over 100 marine laboratories; (iii) Organization of 12 training workshops at the marine stations of Villefranche-sur-Mer (PlanktoScope) and Roscoff (Lamprey), with 115 participants from 61 marine labs; (iv) Co-design of a collective time-series plankton sampling program to be implemented in 2025–2026. A distinctive feature of these workshops was their comprehensive, hands-on approach. Participants were trained in the entire workflow — from plankton sampling and field deployment of the instruments, to data and metadata generation, management, and analysis. This full-process training, spanning from fieldwork to knowledge production, was highly valued by participants. Many have now begun sampling their local ecosystems and have committed to making their data FAIR and publicly available via standardized data papers, enabling transnational and multiscale comparative analyses. Overall, this has been an enriching collective learning experience: the T1.5 team was able to directly test and refine the tools in collaboration with European colleagues, while the trainees gained access to simple and cost-effective protocols that open new possibilities for exploring biodiversity at unprecedented spatial and temporal scales. We also explored all together opportunities to further extend the reach of these tools and bottom-up strategy through future collaborations with marine professionals — including for instance fish farmers, fishers, sailors, and cargo crews.

Annexes

Annex 1 - Email used to invite potential candidates for the Lamprey and the Planktoscope workshops

Dear colleagues,

Are you interested in learning how to use the 'Planktoscope' and/or the 'Lamprey', i.e. innovative, frugal instruments designed to sample and measure plankton morphological and genetic biodiversity in the field and explore unique spatio-temporal scales? Are you willing to contribute, through your local explorations, to a standard and cooperative measure of global plankton life?

*Then, you may want to join one of the workshops that will happen in Fall-2024 and early-2025 at the Villefranche/Mer and Roscoff marine institutes, where **50 PlanktoScopes and Lampreys will be taught and distributed to participants free of charge.***

*Please carefully **fill up this form**. You can read below and see the attached documents for more details on the instruments, workshops, and context.*

<https://form.jotform.com/241332163991051>

Warning: *this form is for information purpose only. It does not guarantee the acquisition of an instrument or participation in a workshop.*

Following the 'Plankton Planet' initiative, we are developing a new generation of cost-effective, handy, and open tools to sample and measure easily the biodiversity of plankton in the field. Two of these instruments, the 'Lamprey' and the 'Planktoscope' allow, respectively, (i) sampling of plankton biomass for genetic analyses back in the lab, and (ii) in-flow quantitative imaging of microplankton. You will find short technical descriptions of both instruments below. The general idea of 'Plankton Planet' is to produce local, standard measures of plankton biodiversity on unique spatio-temporal scales, which are then shared in public databases and thus comparable at global scale.

In the frame of the European project 'BIOcean5D' (<https://www.biocean5d.org/>), we have the opportunity to deploy 50 Planktoscope and Lamprey kits in marine labs along the European coastline. Training in the instruments and associated protocols, from sampling in the field to standard data generation and analyses, will be offered during 3 to 5 days workshops organized in the Villefranche/Mer and Roscoff marine institutes. At the end of the workshop, participants will receive an instrument for free (together with free DNA metabarcodes sequencing for the Lamprey), and be asked to use it following basic community standards. We believe that frugal yet scientifically-sound instruments are a way toward the production of local, high-quality plankton biodiversity data that can contribute to a global measure of plankton life. We hope that this first BIOcean5D deployment will initiate a solid and collaborative community of users, with exchanges of personal know-hows, protocols, and taxonomic knowledge, toward the future use of the 'plankton planet' tools in activities involving local communities and the society.

Please, don't hesitate to forward this message to anyone in your lab / networks who may be interested.

Thanks for your interest and we hope to meet you soon,

The Plankton Planet team -

Annex 2 - Example of detailed program for a Lamprey workshop

<i>Date</i>	<i>Hour</i>	<i>Program</i>
<i>Tue.</i> <i>April</i> <i>15</i>	14:00	Introduction - D. Guiffant, E. Legeay, C. Jeanthon Presentation of the BIOcean5D project and the training program. Presentation by participants (local research activities linked to the workshop's thematic).
	17:00	(Followed by local drink for those who want).
<i>Wed.</i> <i>April</i> <i>16</i>	09:00	Lamprey manipulation - E. Legeay, N. Le Bescot Distribution, set-up, and demonstration.
	12:30	<i>Lunch time</i>
	14:00	Molecular biology - E. Legeay Plankton Planet protocol to generate DNA metabarcodes (DNA extraction, PCR primers, sequencing).
	15:00	Analyses of plankton metaB data - N. Henry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to P2 metaB Data Management Plan • MetaB bioinformatics overview
	17:00	
<i>Thu.</i> <i>April</i> <i>17</i>	09:00	Field plankton sampling - E. Legeay, D. Guiffant, N. Le Bescot. Collection of Roscoff coastal plankton samples, concentration on membranes, conservation. Presentation of other frugal kits (Planktoscope et Curiosity) developed in Plankton Planet
	12:30	<i>Lunch time</i>
	14:00	Analyses of plankton metaB data - N. Henry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MetaB ecological analyses with R (theory) • MetaB ecological analyses with R (practice)
	17:00	
<i>Fri.</i> <i>April</i> <i>18</i>	09:00	Plankton time-series across partner sites with participants from all workshops.
	10:00	Site-specific plans for the use of the Lamprey system in BIOcean5D (80 samples sequenced for free/team). C. Jeanthon, N. Henry.
	12:00	Discussion on future sampling-plan designs by partners.

Annex 3 - Logsheet used to gather standardised metadata related to all Lamprey sampling stations

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15739303>

DECK LOGSHEET - ON SHORE

version 2.0

NAME AREA SITE ID <input style="width:100%;" type="text"/>	NAME SURNAME INVESTIGATOR <input style="width:100%;" type="text"/>	STATION <input style="width:100%;" type="text"/>	
DATE <input style="width:20%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> / <input style="width:20%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> / <input style="width:20%; text-align:center;" type="text"/>	Sea state <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/>	Precipitation <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>	Clouds coverage <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
			Day / Night <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
SAMPLING			CAST <input style="width:100%;" type="text"/>
NET Model : <input type="checkbox"/> MystiNet <input type="checkbox"/> CLASSIC <input type="checkbox"/> HSN <input type="checkbox"/> DIODON <input type="checkbox"/> Tow type : <input type="checkbox"/> HORIZONTAL <input type="checkbox"/> VERTICAL <input type="checkbox"/>			
Other <input style="width:100%;" type="text"/>		Mesh size : <input type="checkbox"/> 20 µm <input type="checkbox"/> 50 µm <input type="checkbox"/> OTHER <input style="width:100%;" type="text"/> µm	
Deployment parameters :			
ROPE ANGLE (Angle vs vertical) <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> °	DEPTH MIN <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> m	DEPTH MAX <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> m	ROPE OUT (in water) <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> m
START			
LAT <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> N/S <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> DD° <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> MM.MMM'	LONG <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> E/W <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> DD° <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> MM.MMM'	UTC TIME <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> HH <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> MM	
END			
LAT <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> N/S <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> DD° <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> MM.MMM'	LONG <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> E/W <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> DD° <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> MM.MMM'	UTC TIME <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> HH <input style="width:10%; text-align:center;" type="text"/> MM	
COMMENTS			
ADDITIONAL INFOS			
NET TOW SPEED <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> knots		CTD Model <input style="width:100%;" type="text"/>	
ROPE OUT <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> m		ROPE OUT <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> m	
AIR T° <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> °C	FLOWMETER Model <input style="width:100%;" type="text"/>		START <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/>
SEA WATER T° <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> °C			END <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/>
WIND SPEED <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> knots			
WIND DIRECTION <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> °	SECCHI DISC		
WAVE DIRECTION <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> °	DISAPPEARING POINT <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> m	AGAIN SIGHTED <input style="width:20%;" type="text"/> m	
COMMENTS			

DECK LOGSHEET - ON SHORE

version 2.0

FILTRATION TREATMENT		FINAL VOLUME AFTER NET RINSING : <input style="width: 50px;" type="text" value="000"/> mL
FILTER n°1	Porosity : <input style="width: 50px;" type="text" value="00.0"/> μm	BARCODE
START TIME UTC <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="HH"/> <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="MM"/>	END TIME UTC <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="HH"/> <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="MM"/>	TUBE ID <input style="width: 150px;" type="text" value="NAME"/>
FILTERED VOLUME <input style="width: 50px;" type="text" value="000"/> mL	Saturation : YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>	
FILTER n°2	Porosity : <input style="width: 50px;" type="text" value="00.0"/> μm	BARCODE
START TIME UTC <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="HH"/> <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="MM"/>	END TIME UTC <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="HH"/> <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="MM"/>	TUBE ID <input style="width: 150px;" type="text" value="NAME"/>
FILTERED VOLUME <input style="width: 50px;" type="text" value="000"/> mL	Saturation : YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/>	
COMMENTS		
IMAGING TREATMENT		FINAL VOLUME AFTER NET RINSING : <input style="width: 50px;" type="text" value="000"/> mL
FIRST	PROJECT NAME <input style="width: 150px;" type="text" value="NAME"/>	STATION ID <input style="width: 80px;" type="text" value="STATION + CAST (000-000)"/>
Acq ID ti import <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="000"/>	Nb of images <input style="width: 40px;" type="text" value="0000"/>	Nb of Objects <input style="width: 40px;" type="text" value="0000"/>
		DILUTION <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="0"/>
SECOND	PROJECT NAME <input style="width: 150px;" type="text" value="NAME"/>	STATION ID <input style="width: 80px;" type="text" value="STATION + CAST (000-000)"/>
Acq ID ti import <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="000"/>	Nb of images <input style="width: 40px;" type="text" value="0000"/>	Nb of Objects <input style="width: 40px;" type="text" value="0000"/>
		DILUTION <input style="width: 30px;" type="text" value="0"/>
COMMENTS		

Annex 4 - Example of a taxonomic sheet being produced thanks to the reference project in Ecotaxa - Planktoscope

Ornithocercus (Phylo)

from FlowCamMicro/PlanktoScope

living > Eukaryota > Harosa > Alveolata > Myzozoa > Holodinochyta > Dinophyceae > Dinophysiales > Dinophysaceae > Oxyphysaceae > Ornithocercus

Published on 19 May 2025

Written by Sophie Marro

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MORPHOLOGICAL IDENTIFICATION

Ornithocercus Stein, 1883

Ornithocercus genus belongs to **Dinophyceae** class.

Ornithocercus have a small to **medium-size body** with **extensive list and rib systems** that characterize the species. The cell have a diameter of **30-80 µm** but the lists and ribs can **double** the total size of the cell.

This genus didn't have **chloroplasts** but they can have **photosynthetic symbionts** in the cingular chamber.

DESCRIPTIVE SCHEMAS

Lateral view (Planktoscope)

Legend :

- APICAL LIST
- CENTRAL BODY
- RIBS

MORE EXAMPLES

Lateral view (Flowcam)

Legend :

- APICAL LIST
- CENTRAL BODY
- RIBS

MORE EXAMPLES

Dorsal view (Flowcam)

Legend :

- CENTRAL BODY
- APICAL LIST
- RIBS

Lateral view (Planktoscope)

PHOTOGRAPHIES & FIGURES

1. https://www.algaebase.org/search/images/detail?img_id=16476. *Ornithocercus splendidus* F.Schütt - 04 February 2011. John Dolan (dolan@obs-vlfr.fr)

About EcoTaxoGuide

If you use EcoTaxoGuide in your work, we would appreciate if you cite it as : Elineau A., Picheral M., Coustenoble J. (2024) EcoTaxoGuide, Guides for taxonomic identification based on images : <https://ecotaxoguide.imev-mer.fr>

EcoTaxoGuide was developed thanks to the support of the following organizations and projects :

We would very much appreciate if you would consider setting aside some funds in your next grant for this. Contact us to estimate what would be both reasonable and useful. The people behind the development of EcoTaxoGuide are :

- Amanda Elineau, Marc Picheral and Laurent Salinas: specifications
- Amanda Elineau, Julie Coustenoble and Marc Picheral : project supervision
- ITLINK : development
- PIQV and the COMPLEX team from Institut de la Mer de Villefranche (IMEV) and Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV): testing and feedback

